

DOORS

Developing Optimal and Open Research Support for the Black Sea

Project Information

URL: www.doorsblacksea.eu

Project Coordinator: GeoEcoMar

Coordinator Country: Romania

Project duration: 1/06/2021- 31/5/2025

Funding Programme H2020-EU-3.2.3.3 - Boosting marine and maritime innovation through biotechnology

Project mission

DOORS (Developing Optimal and Open Research Support for the Black Sea) is a research project that links citizens, science, and industry for critical Black Sea regeneration, stimulating a new wave of blue economy opportunities. In particular, the project aims to harmonise scientific approaches and policy across all Black Sea nations while bringing access to state-of-the-art satellite technology that allows a better understanding of the entire Black Sea.

Type of synergy

Contribution to Blue-Cloud Roadmap: DOORS has shared inputs and best practices for the development of the Blue-Cloud strategic Roadmap.

Usage and exploitation of Blue-Cloud VRE services: Blue-Cloud and DOORS have explored the possibility of creating a dedicated Vlab in the Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment ("VRE") in order to perform dedicated analysis for Black Sea data. A number of meetings took place to discuss the technical requirements and potential benefits. However, due to the impact of the war in Ukraine, activities have been delayed.

Data Discovery and Access Service: Blue-Cloud and DOORS have also discussed how new Black Sea data to be collected by DOORS might become part of the Blue-Cloud DD&AS. Blue-Cloud has strongly recommended to DOORS to manage the new data first of all in the Black Sea NODCs and then to make use of the European BDIs such as SeaDataNet and EurOBIS for sharing the new data at European level. This way, the new data will automatically become part of the Blue-Cloud federation. The DOORS Black Sea partners have agreed with this approach and strategy for new data; however, due to the war situation in the Black Sea region, it was not been possible to undertake project cruises as earlier planned. In the meantime, the dialogue between Blue-Cloud and DOORS is continued and for instance, there were several presentations contributed by SeaDataNet and Blue-Cloud to the MARBLUE Conference, organised in Romania, 26-28 October 2022.

Factsheet available at <https://blue-cloud.org/synergies/doors>